

**THE NORTHERN VECTOR OF THE IRANIAN ISLAMIC REVOLUTION: THE
IMPACT OF AZERBAIJAN AND TURKMENISTAN ON FOREIGN POLICY AND
CULTURAL DYNAMICS DURING INDEPENDENCE
(1991-2000)**

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Summary: *This work analyzes the impact of the Iranian Islamic Revolution of 1979 on the foreign policy and cultural dynamics of the post-Soviet space, especially in the period of independence of Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan (1991-2000). The study attempted to examine the challenges and opportunities posed by Iran's post-revolutionary theocratic ideology in relations with its northern neighbors. The balance between Iran's attempts at religious influence and regional relations against the backdrop of Azerbaijan's secular statehood tradition and Turkmenistan's permanent neutrality status has been comparatively reviewed. Thus, we will dwell on these issues in several places: the legal status of the Caspian Sea, the "contract of the century", energy projects and the influence of ethnic factors (Turkmens and Azerbaijan) on the security sphere are the central lines of the article. The main purpose here is not just to analyze the relationship between states, but also to investigate how the Islamic Revolution in Iran in the region has manifested itself in the coming decades. In general, it is emphasized how the ideological pressure in the relations of both states with Iran is neutralized through economic cooperation.*

Key words: *Iran Islamic Revolution, Azerbaijan-Iran relations, Turkmenistan-Iran relations, Post-Soviet geopolitics, Caspian legal status, Energy Diplomacy, permanent neutrality.*

Introduction.

One of the events that left a unique mark in history was the Islamic Revolution of Iran, which took place in 1979. The revolution affected not only the formation of the theocratic model of power in the domestic political system of Iran. It has also redefined Iran's regional ambitions, ideological policy and security concept. This, in turn, had an important impact on the life of states located in the border region with Iran. These processes created new challenges and opportunities in the post-Soviet independence period, especially for Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan, which have historical, cultural and geopolitical ties with Iran. After gaining independence in 1991, both states began to pursue a balanced policy between regional centers of power such as, Iran, Turkey and Russia. Iran's foreign policy course after the 1979 Revolution played a special role in their security architecture, energy projects, border cooperation, religious and humanitarian influences and geopolitical dynamics of the South Caucasus-Central Asia region. In this context, the main problem is to determine how decisive the ideological and geopolitical effects caused by The Revolution are in the relations of independent Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan with Iran.

In this regard, if we look at each state separately, we should bring to the fore a number of points in the context of geopolitical and border security of Iran-Turkmenistan relations. Thus, Turkmenistan, which had just declared its independence in 1991, began to form as a new geopolitical factor in Central Asia. The country, which has an area of 488,100 square kilometers and does not have direct access to the high seas, divides the border with Iran, which in modern times exceeds 1,200 kilometers. Thus, this geographical position has made Turkmenistan a strategic bridge for Iran in terms of access to Central Asia, bringing the two countries closer to the position of natural partners, especially in negotiations on the legal status of the Caspian Sea.

The Iran-Turkmenistan border has not only geographical, but also ethno-religious features. While the majority of Turkmens belong to the Sunni-Hanafi sect, the main population of Iran is Shi'ite. In particular, the Turkmen communities living in the Gulustan region and the Turkmen desert are ethnically, linguistically and religiously closely connected with their co-rulers in Turkmenistan. This factor makes the border both a sociocultural Bridge and a vulnerable zone. Therefore, the revolutions that took place within Iran directly affected Turkmenistan.

The situation in Azerbaijan is almost no different. However, it should be noted that while secularism in other former Soviet Muslim republics was mainly applied by the Soviet authorities in administrative and ideological ways, secularism in Azerbaijan was a product of local intellectual processes that took shape in an earlier period in the late XIX and early XX centuries. This feature plays a key role in understanding the religious and political dynamics of the country even during the Islamic Revolution in Iran. The National intelligentsia formed at the beginning of the twentieth century had long-term ideological rivalry with the spiritual class and took the position of Public Leadership. In this process, the ideology of Turkism and national modernism gradually removed religious identity from the political center, and Islam began to be perceived more as a cultural-identity component. This trend is especially clearly observed during the period of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, which existed in 1918-1920. The model of the first parliamentary republic in the Muslim East, despite the presence of Islamist political forces, took as a basis the principle of secular legislation, and not the construction of the legal system on the basis of Sharia.

After the establishment of Bolshevik power, the anticlerical (that is, opposition to the interference of the clergy in state affairs), intellectual environment, which had already formed in Azerbaijani Society, played a role in the stricter implementation of Soviet atheistic policy. Unlike other Muslim regions, the weakening of religious institutions in Azerbaijan has become faster and more systematic. And this facilitated the suppression of religion in the socio-political sphere in Soviet times.[11]

As for the revival of Islam in the post Soviet period, the growth of religious activity here can be regarded not only as a “reversal of the repressed faith”, but also as its formation with influences from foreign religious centers especially Iran, Turkey and Arab countries. However, in general, this factor necessitates a separate analysis of Iran’s ideological policy in the context of Azerbaijan after the effects of the Iranian Islamic Revolution of 1979.

The main interests that unite Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan in the context of relations with Iran are not limited to the geopolitical position, energy resources, border security and maintaining the regional balance are the main policies of both countries. Both states sought to maintain stable neighborhood relations after independence, given the long land border with Iran, and also pursued a balanced policy towards other regional states, such as Russia and Turkey. The legal status of the Caspian Sea, energy export routes and transit opportunities were strategic factors that necessitated cooperation with Iran for both Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan.

The main purpose of the study is to comprehensively analyze the impact of the 1979 Iranian Islamic Revolution on the relations of Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan with Iran during the period of independence. For this purpose: determination of the new geopolitical environment caused by the ideological and political consequences of the revolution for the regional states, analysis of religious, political, economic and security aspects in Azerbaijan–Iran and Turkmenistan–Iran relations are considered important points. In addition, the article attempts to address issues such as formation of difficulties and opportunities for cooperation in the Post-revolutionary Iran’s foreign policy model in the Post-Soviet space, assessment of the strategic directions of Iran’s South Caucasus and Central Asia policy after 1991.

A brief overview of the history of the Iranian Revolution. Religious-cultural influence. The Iranian revolution is an important historical event that took place in 1979 and led to radical changes in the political system of Iran. As a result of the revolution, Mohammad Reza Pahlavi was removed from power, the monarchical regime was abolished and a new political system based on Islamic principles was established. The ideological leader of the revolution was Ruhollah Khomeini, and

under his leadership a theocratic state model was formed in Iran. This event not only changed the internal political structure of Iran, but also had a significant impact on the country's foreign policy directions and relations with the states of the region.

The Islamic Revolution of 1979 provided an opportunity to redefine and strengthen Iran's Shiite identity. After the revolution, the foreign policy of the Islamic Republic of Iran was formed on the basis of the "Islamic-Shiite theories" put forward by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini. Known as the founder of the Shiite Islamic system and a charismatic leader, Khomeini managed to unite around himself all political parties, socio-political roles, state institutions and various strata of society. [3]

In accordance with this goal, the International Conference of Islamic Liberation Movements was held in Tehran in 1980 and the Supreme Coordination Council of foreign Islamic Revolutions was established. In addition, the establishment of institutions such as the permanent Hajj Services Committee, the International Congress of Friday Imams and the International Bureau of Islamic propaganda indicates that Iran's foreign policy is shaped on religious and spiritual grounds.

Consequently, just as the internal political principles of the Islamic Republic of Iran are aimed at combating Islamic values and social injustice, its foreign policy is formulated in the same ideological spirit. This approach is also clearly reflected in the views of Imam Khomeini. In one of his speeches, emphasizing that the Islamic Revolution is not limited to the national level, he said: "Our Revolution should be a source of hope not only for Iran, but for all oppressed peoples." [3]

Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan, located in the northern direction of Iran, were among the countries affected to some extent by these processes. When both states gained independence after the collapse of the USSR in 1991, Iran was already formed as a state with ideological and regional ambitions. This situation created both opportunities for cooperation and certain cautious approaches in their relations with Iran.

For Azerbaijan, the influence of the Iranian Revolution was mainly felt in ideological and political aspects. Thus, in particular, the population living in the south of Azerbaijan was influenced by Iran's religious policy. Here, the values adopted by Khomeini were welcomed by the population. Nevertheless, a number of decisions were made on religion by the state, and it was considered unacceptable to go to extremes in religion. As an example, we can mention the restriction of the ceremonies held in Iran during the month of Muharram in Azerbaijan and the organization of blood donation actions instead. As a result, Azerbaijan pursued a cautious policy against possible religious influence from Tehran. At the same time, cooperation between the two countries in the fields of border, trade and energy continued.

This issue was also important for Turkmenistan. Despite the atheistic policy of the Soviet Union, the Iranian revolution created a kind of "encouragement" among the Muslim population in the region. After the revolution, opinions spread among some religious groups in the southern regions of Turkmenistan that Islam could be a political power. However, unlike Azerbaijan, the Turkmens began to realize their Islamic identity more during this period, as a result of which the Iranian "Shiite" revolution was not fully perceived by the "Sunni" Turkmens as an ideological model.

In the Post-Soviet period, however, the influence of the Iranian Islamic Revolution on Turkmenistan shifted more to the plane of interstate relations and cultural diplomacy. Independent Turkmenistan tried to use to its advantage not the "ideological" side of the revolution, but the regional power and cultural proximity created by it.

Since Turkmenistan has a Sunni religious environment and a policy of neutrality, the ideological factor in relations with Iran has been relatively weak, focusing on border security, energy cooperation and transit opportunities. Energy and economic cooperation between Iran and Turkmenistan has created conditions for the development of relations, especially in the field of gas. [8]

The Organization of Islamic Cooperation plays a special role in taking steps in the cultural sphere. Since 1991, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan became members of this organization since 1992. One of the most extensive steps taken within the framework of this membership was the promotion of the Karabakh issue among Muslim states. At the same time, Turkmenistan has acted more as a

representative of peacekeeping and humanism over the years, acting on its policy of “permanent neutrality”. Iran, on the other hand, tried to see the OIC as an anti-imperialist center of the Islamic world in line with its post-revolutionary political doctrine, but in the face of Azerbaijan’s growing regional influence and Turkmenistan’s “permanent neutrality” status, it was forced to opt more for Economic Partnership (e.g. gas and transport corridors). Turkmenistan’s place in this triangle is to stay away from religious-political polarizations within the organization, as well as to present Islamic identity as an element of its national diplomacy. The cooperation of these three states on the OIC platform is once again crossed, especially at intersections with the Organization for Economic Cooperation (OIC/ECO).

Thus, the Iranian Revolution of 1979 was an important event that changed the political landscape of the region, and its influence was also reflected in the foreign policy priorities of the states located in the South Caucasus and Central Asia. Although Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan responded to these influences with different political models, both countries tried to pursue a pragmatic and balanced policy in relations with Iran.

Impact on the foreign policy vector.

The Iranian revolution fundamentally changed the directions of Iran’s foreign policy and influenced the formation of a new strategy in relation to the post-Soviet space, especially after 1991. One of the main issues that have made Iran important for us during these periods is to know not only the interests of neighboring countries in its foreign policy position, but also their interests against the West. In addition to the established relations with Russia, the relations with the United States have a strong impact on the region in this regard.

John L. Esposito and James Piscatori – Iranian Revolution ten years later: what was its global impact? His work notes: “no one can deny the long-term compatible interests of the United States and Iran. Iran has obvious strategic importance due to its territory (by the beginning of the century its population will be twice the population of the Gulf countries), oil and gas wealth, proximity to the Soviet Union and dominance of the vital Strait of Hormuz. Given these factors, Iran has the ability to influence Gulf regional stability and, in a broad sense, the interests of the United States.”[7.27]

According to the idea of another author -, and the fall of the Soviet Union changed all these interests: , “so it put Iran with three unstable neighbors-Azerbaijan, Armenia and Turkmenistan – and a few more distant and equally unstable neighbors in the South Caucasus and Central Asia. Two of these neighbors – Armenia and Azerbaijan were involved in the controversial (according to the author) armed conflict for the Nagorno-Karabakh region. This conflict made Iran face unpleasant political choices. Nevertheless, Tehran at that time began to establish active diplomatic relations in the northern direction. For example, in 1992, Iran established diplomatic relations with Azerbaijan, and during the same period a number of preliminary agreements on economic and trade cooperation were signed between the two countries. In addition, in 1992, Iran initiated mediation in the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and organized negotiations between representatives of Azerbaijan and Armenia in Tehran.” [9].

However, Iran has been indifferent to such processes as the influx of refugees from Azerbaijan. This was one of the main reasons that increased the tension in the region. Because Azerbaijan, which had just gained independence, intended to settle this chaos, but these provocations led to a weakening of morale. The capture of the city of Shusha, the eye of Azerbaijan, was almost equal to the capture of Karabakh as a whole. At such a time, despite the adoption of UN – mediated resolutions, the cold attitude continued.

In addition, Iran faced new security threats because some of Iran’s ethnic minorities coincided with the populations of these post-Soviet republics, especially Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan, and because of Azerbaijan’s and potentially Turkmenistan’s territorial irredentism towards Iranian territories. [11.120-121]

The issue we should mention here was that thousands of people with Turkic ethnic identities lived in the territory of South Azerbaijan. *So, a smaller group of Iranian Turks , the Turkmen ethnic group, lives mainly in the northeastern regions of Iran, including in areas along the eastern coast of*

the Caspian Sea and the southern border of Turkmenistan. Known as the "Turkmen-desert" or Turkmen desert, this region constitutes their main habitat within Iran.[5] At the same time, thousands of Azerbaijani Turks lived in the north of Iran. It was in this regard, as Hunter emphasized, that ethnic minorities caused Iran to face security threats. The unification and uprising of the Turkish population living here could be considered unacceptable for Iran. To prevent this, it was necessary to take serious steps not only in the post – Soviet period, but also before that. One of the main issues that we should emphasize here is related to the teaching of Azerbaijani Turkish. If we briefly touch on this topic, we should note that even in the post-Soviet period (i.e. from 1991 to the present day), the ban on systematic education in Azerbaijani Turkish in Iran remained essentially unchanged. Azerbaijani Turkish is a language that is understandable not only among the Turks living in Azerbaijan, but also among the Turkic peoples in general. In particular, there are great similarities between Turkmen and this language. In other words, it is clear again that a policy has been pursued that seeks to destroy the national identity of a people by taking away their language. This, in turn, was a factor of concern for both republics in the neighborhood.

Despite all this, as we emphasized earlier, there were interests that united all three states in the region. Thus, in the post – Soviet period, the construction of a number of energy infrastructure projects began. One of the main projects for Azerbaijan here was related to the contract of the century. Initially, Iran was expected to hold a 5% stake during negotiations on this agreement. So, at that time, the United States imposed harsh sanctions on Iran for its nuclear program and other political reasons. The United States stated that if Iran participates in the project, American companies will withdraw from the contract and financial support will be cut. As a result, Iran could not get this share in order to ensure the establishment of relations with the West. After that, it was transferred to Turkey, and Turkey's share in this project increased. But Iran could not remain silent about this treaty. Thus, the issue of the status of the Caspian Sea was raised. Iran tried to prevent the export of oil, contributing to the fact that the distribution of the region was achieved during the Soviet period. Nevertheless, this policy of his ended in failure. It is noteworthy that although he could not participate in the "contract of the century", Iran was able to become a shareholder in another major project of Azerbaijan – the Shah Deniz gas field. *Thus, the Iranian company NICO currently has a 10% stake in "Shah Deniz".*[1.1]

At the same time, one of the important directions in Iran's Northern policy was Relations with Turkmenistan. In the early 1990s, Iran began to establish cooperation with Turkmenistan in the field of energy and transport. The opening of the Korpeje–Kordkuy gas pipeline between the two countries in 1997 is considered one of the first major projects of energy cooperation between Iran and Turkmenistan, which enabled the supply of Turkmen gas to the Iranian market. [8]

Apart from related economic and infrastructure relations, historical and cultural ties, these two countries have common security concerns. Turkmenistan and Iran have firm positions against Sunni Islamists and ISIS. Sharing a long border, Turkmenistan is an important partner of Iran to prevent threats to and from the Central Asian region. Afghanistan is another area of cooperation between Ashgabat and Tehran in the field of security in the field of terrorism, drug production and smuggling. [5]

One of the points that we should mention here is related to the "cold" position between Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan in the issue of the status of the Caspian Sea, which we emphasized earlier: "since 2005, he proposed dividing the Caspian Sea along the middle line, but failed to reach an agreement with Azerbaijan in a number of directions. The Turkmen side claims that the Caspian Sea should be divided on the principle of the middle line and serve as a border between these states. In world practice, there is also the practice of determining the middle line taking into account "special situations". These "special circumstances" create some obstacles to the implementation of the UN Convention on the definition of sea borders, adopted in 1982. Taking this factor into account, Ashgabat believes that the Absheron Peninsula and Chilov island should not be taken into account when dividing the Caspian Sea between Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan. Of course, the Azerbaijani side did not agree with this principle." [4]

In addition, the International North-South Transport Corridor (BSHND) probably contributed to the growth of Tehran-Baku cooperation in the Caspian region. The last step of this reconstruction is the planned gas supplies from Turkmenistan to Turkey via Iran.[5]

Thus, the ideological and political principles formulated by the Islamic Revolution in Iran manifested themselves in the northern direction after 1991-especially in relations with Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan – in the form of specific diplomatic initiatives, energy projects and regional mediation activities.

Conclusion. The theocratic doctrine formulated by the Islamic Revolution of Iran of 1979 was both an ideological test and a factor of strategic balance in the foreign policy of Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan, which gained independence after 1991. The study shows that Azerbaijan’s deep-rooted secularism tradition and Turkmenistan’s “permanent neutrality” status served as an effective shield against Iran’s revolutionary “export” tendencies, and both states removed religious identity from the political center and protected it in the context of cultural and spiritual heritage. The dynamics between 1991 and 2000 prove that in the light of the status of the Caspian Sea, energy and transport projects such as the “contract of the century” and Korpeje–Kordkuy, geo-economic interests overcame ideological acuteness, as a result of which Baku and Ashgabat managed to transfer relations with Iran to the plane of a pragmatic neighborhood. Ethnic Turkmen and Azerbaijani Turkic factors within Iran have prompted these states to be more sensitive to the principles of mutual security and non-interference in internal affairs, contributing to the establishment of a fragile but stable balance of power in the region.

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